

Studying the smelting behaviour of bauxite residue pellets reduced by hydrogen using high temperature thermal analysis

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ABSTRACT

Treating bauxite residue as an alternative source of metals for iron and aluminium industry is an approach to promote circular economy in metal industries. Reduction of metal oxides with H₂-based process is an important step on decarbonisation of metal industry. In this study bauxite residue pellets were prepared and were reduced with different H₂-H₂O gas compositions at different temperatures which yielded with various degrees of reduction. The bauxite residue pellets were made from a mixture of bauxite residue and Ca(OH)₂ powders and sintered at 1150°C. Hydrogen reduction was carried out on the oxide pellets using a resistance furnace at elevated temperatures in controlled reduction atmosphere of H₂-H₂O gas mixtures which resulted in reduction of iron oxides in the pellets. Unreduced and reduced pellets were subsequently heated to 1400°C to study their smelting behaviour using differential thermal analysis (DTA) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) technique to investigate the evolution of phases related to slag formation via smelting. Equilibrium module of Factsage™ ver 8.1 was utilised to analyse results of thermal analysis. It was observed that Tricalcium phosphate-β (CaP₂O₈), Bredigite (Ca₇Si₄MgO₁₆), Rankinite (Ca₃Si₂O₇), and calcium alumino ferrite (Ca[Al,Fe]₆O₁₀) were formed during thermal analysis as intermediate phases. The initial slag formation for sintered and reduced pellets occurred at 900°C which mainly contains calcium and small amount of strontium component. The slag formation rate increases significantly starting from 1100°C when iron oxides started to form initial molten slag phase which then followed by other oxides dissolution in the system. Gas formation was observed at 1180°C and it was found that the gas to be released from unreduced pellets is O₂ meanwhile the gas to be released from reduced pellets is SO₂ gas. Gas formation rate for both pellets start to increase at 1280°C when the remaining chemically bonded gas start to be released from the system.

INTRODUCTION

Bayer process and bauxite residue

The Bayer process was invented and patented by Carl Josef Bayer in 1888 and has since then been the leading process for alumina (Al₂O₃) production in the world. The process consists of eight main stages: milling, desilication, digestion, clarification, precipitation, evaporation, classification and calcination. In the milling step, the bauxite ore is crushed down into finer particles. Additionally, limestone is added to create a pumpable slurry. After the milling step, the slurry moves through a process called desilication, which involves removing silica (SiO₂). The slurry is then digested using a NaOH solution, which dissolves the aluminium bearing minerals in the bauxite. These minerals include gibbsite (Al(OH)₃), boehmite (γ-AlO(OH)) and diasporite (α-AlO(OH)). When the solution is added, the following reactions take place with gibbsite and boehmite/diasporite, given by Equation (1) and Equation (2) respectively (Smallman and Bishop, 1999):

After the processing step, the slurry is cooled down using a series of flash tanks at 1 atm. The slurry is then prepared for clarification where the bauxite residue (BR) is separated away through sedimentation, where chemical additives assist in driving the BR to the bottom of the settling tanks. BR is transferred to washing tanks, where the goal is to recover the caustic soda used in the digestion step. The saturated liquid undergoes a series of filtration steps and BR is left in disposal areas. After

clarification, alumina is recovered through crystallisation during precipitation step. The precipitation reaction is shown in Equation (3) (Smallman and Bishop, 1999):

Evaporation of the liquid used during crystallisation takes place in heat exchangers, where it is subsequently cooled down afterwards in flash tanks. The condensate that is created through this process is reused for BR washing or as feed water. Recovered caustic soda is then re-added to the digestion step. The crystals are classified into size ranges, using cyclones and gravity classification tanks. For the coarse crystals, separation from liquid and calcination is performed. For the finer crystals, washing to remove organic impurities and re-addition to the precipitation step is performed. Calcination of the coarse crystals is done by roasting in calciners. The roasting process takes place at temperatures up to 1100°C. This drives off moisture and water, which eventually creates alumina solids. The calcination reaction is shown in Equation (4) (Smallman and Bishop, 1999):

Smelting reduction of bauxite residue

Red mud, also known as bauxite residue (BR) in dewatered form, is the main by-product generated in the Bayer process. Typically, for each tonne of produced alumina from bauxite ore, about 1.5 t of BR is produced (Pandey and Prakash, 2020). The generated BR from the Bayer process is stored in large holding ponds, where only 1 per cent to 2 per cent is being recycled (Brunori *et al*, 2005). Dried BR typically contains up to 50 per cent of iron oxides. Other compounds found in BR includes silica oxides, titanium oxides, aluminium oxides and other oxides. It is also highly alkaline, with a pH level ranging from 12–13. Due to its high alkalinity, red mud that is stored away in holding ponds poses a great environmental threat to its surroundings. The main way of treating the alkaline BR, is to attempt neutralising by adding acidic substances, such as HCl (Brunori *et al*, 2005).

Smelting reduction of BR opens opportunities for recovery of its metal content, especially iron (Liu *et al*, 2021), aluminium (Lazou *et al*, 2021) and rare-earth elements (REEs) (Borra *et al*, 2016). It is to be understood from previous research that removal of iron content is a necessary preliminary step for effective recovery of alumina and REEs in BR (Lazou *et al*, 2021; Borra *et al*, 2016) and smelting reduction is believed to be the most efficient method for removal of iron in BR. Several studies on smelting reduction of BR have been conducted within the past decade which mainly tries to recover iron content in BR either in the form of magnetite (Lazou *et al*, 2021) or metallic iron (Kar, van der Eijk and Safarian, 2022; Skibelid *et al*, 2022; Lazou *et al*, 2021; Ekstroem *et al*, 2021; Borra *et al*, 2016).

Smelting reduction of BR with H₂ at low temperature (480°C) was able to produce magnetite with 87 per cent conversion degree with insignificant metallic iron production (Samouhos *et al*, 2017). Meanwhile smelting reduction with H₂ at high temperature (1000°C) was able to completely reduce Fe content in BR to metallic Fe (Kar, van der Eijk and Safarian, 2022; Skibelid *et al*, 2022). However, the recovery of Fe-containing phases from solid-state reduced BR remains an issue due to its physical nature which exists in miniscule spots with less than 20 µm in particle diameter (Kar, van der Eijk and Safarian, 2022; Skibelid *et al*, 2022). Carbothermic reduction of BR beyond Fe melting point (>1538°C) was able to reliably produce pig iron in its own separated phase (Lazou *et al*, 2021; Ekstroem *et al*, 2021). The remaining issue was recovery of Al content from its slag where almost half of it was trapped in Gehlenite (Al₂Ca₂O₇Si) phase which is difficult to recover via hydrometallurgical means (Lazou *et al*, 2021).

Previous studies showed that temperature of smelting reduction plays a key role in determining final phase composition and state of reduced BR. Smelting reduction beyond Fe melting point can reliably produce pig iron in separated phase, but it will also produce unleachable slag which significantly lowers its valourisation potential. Meanwhile heat treating in solid state has its own challenges which mainly revolves around separation process of metallic iron which distributed throughout BR in miniscule spots (Kar, van der Eijk and Safarian, 2022; Skibelid *et al*, 2022). Thus, the aim of present study is to assess change in phase compositions of BR and smelted BR with increasing temperature through comparison of experimental data and thermochemistry simulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An experimental procedure was designed to study smelting behaviour of BR pellets which has been reduced by hydrogen. A mix of BR and Ca(OH)_2 was made and pelletised, then they were sintered. The sintered pellets were reduced under different $\text{H}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ gas mixtures. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) were employed to analyse phase composition of sintered pellets, meanwhile only XRD was employed to analyse phase composition of reduced pellets. A single pellet from the sintered pellets and reduced pellets was then crushed and sieved under 1 mm for differential thermal analysis (DTA) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) to analyse smelting behaviour of sintered and reduced pellets with increasing temperature up to 1400°C.

Pelletising and sintering

BR fines were deagglomerated and screened (<250 μm) to obtain uniform sizing on the mixing process. Raw CaCO_3 powder was calcined to make CaO powder. Resulting CaO powder was ground and screened (<250 μm) before it was hydrated to make Ca(OH)_2 powder. BR fines were mixed with Ca(OH)_2 powder with a mass ratio of 1:0.38 respectively. The ratio was decided based on the stoichiometric ratio of CaO needed to effectively produce calcium aluminate phase in the reduced pellets to allow effective recovery of alumina through leaching. The green pellets were made using a disc pelletiser and screened to obtain pellets with diameter of 4–10 mm which then air-dried for one day and subsequently sintered at 1150°C for 2 hrs in a muffle furnace. The sintered pellets were cooled down naturally inside the furnace for 8 hrs before taken out. Flow sheet of the pelletising and sintering process is shown in Figure 1, meanwhile XRF analysis of raw BR, CaCO_3 powder and sintered pellet are shown in Tables 1 to 3, respectively.

TABLE 1

XRF analysis of raw BR, dry basis (normalised).

Composition	Wt%	Composition	Wt%
CaO	9.98	TiO ₂	5.67
MgO	0.26	Na ₂ O	3.51
SiO ₂	8.05	K ₂ O	0.10
Al ₂ O ₃	24.94	P ₂ O ₅	0.13
Fe ₂ O ₃	46.20	SO ₃	1.07
MnO	0.09	Total	100

*Excluding Loss of Ignition (LOI)

TABLE 2

XRF analysis of raw CaCO_3 powder, dry basis (normalised).

Composition	Wt%	Composition	Wt%
CaO	98.632	TiO ₂	0.005
MgO	0.547	Na ₂ O	0.037
SiO ₂	0.208	K ₂ O	0.035
Al ₂ O ₃	0.175	P ₂ O ₅	0.009
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.084	SO ₃	0.263
MnO	0.005	Total	100

*Excluding Loss of Ignition (LOI)

TABLE 3
XRF analysis of sintered BR pellet.

Composition	Wt%	Composition	Wt%	Composition	Wt%
CaO	29.01	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.18	P ₂ O ₅	0.12
MgO	0.37	V ₂ O ₅	0.15	SO ₃	1.03
SiO ₂	7.66	TiO ₂	3.87	ZrO ₂	0.11
Al ₂ O ₃	23.12	NiO	0.06	SrO	0.03
Fe ₂ O ₃	30.52	Na ₂ O	3.61	Co ₃ O ₄	0.02
MnO	0.04	K ₂ O	0.10	Total	100

FIG 1 – Flow sheet of the pelletising and sintering process.

H2 reduction

The reduction experiments were conducted using a vertical alumina tube resistance furnace with an outer metallic alloy heating element. Around 20 g of sintered pellet was used in every experiment. Shown in Figure 2 is both the furnace and a schematic of its inside. The furnace consists of a cylinder-shaped alumina tube, surrounded by an element that is twined around the furnace. A thermocouple is inserted from the top of the furnace to measure the temperature of the sample holder. The sample holder is made from alumina with gas distributor attached at the bottom to ensure uniform gas distribution to the sample bed. The furnace features a reduction gas inlet positioned at its lower section which goes directly to the sample holder, while the gas, having interacted with the sample, is subsequently leaves through the top gas outlet of the furnace. Another gas inlet at lower section of the furnace which does not go to the sample holder is used to flush the furnace with Argon gas at all times of the experiment to prevent water vapor accumulation in the furnace chamber. The heating and cooling were programmed, while the temperature changes were collected by data logging.

FIG 2 – Picture and schematic diagram of reduction furnace.

H₂-H₂O gas mixture composition was controlled by flowing H₂ gas through a humidifier with set humidity value. The humidifier is P-10 model made by Cellkraft™ AB with membrane technology. Experiments were done in three different H₂-H₂O gas compositions at 600°C as shown in Table 4. Heating rate of the furnace was 10°C/min and held for 2 hrs at set reduction temperature. Total flow of H₂-H₂O gas mix was kept at 1 L/min at all experiments and the furnace was flushed with 1L/min of argon at all times, including the cooling and heating period. Schematic heating diagram of the experiment is shown in Figure 3.

TABLE 4

Experiment conditions for H₂ reduction.

No.	Gas composition (vol%)	Reduction temperature (°C)
1	95% H ₂ – 5% H ₂ O	600
2	85% H ₂ – 15% H ₂ O	600
3	75% H ₂ – 25% H ₂ O	600

FIG 3 – Heating diagram of H₂ reduction experiment.

Thermal analysis

To simulate a smelting process, samples from sintered and reduced BR were subjected to heat treatment up to 1400°C under inert atmosphere. A single pellet from each hydrogen reduction experiment and the sintered pellet were grinded and sieved to <1 mm in preparation for DTA and TGA analysis. Two hundred milligrams of sample were used for every analysis. Both DTA and TGA analysis were carried out at the same time using LINSEIS™ TG-DTA equipment by putting the sample inside an alumina crucible. It is expected that the surface of alumina crucible which is in contact with the sample might react with the sample, promoting reactions with alumina as reactant or hindering reactions with alumina as product. However, considering the alumina content in the sample, although quantitative analysis on the result would be inaccurate due to reaction between the sample and the alumina crucible, it should not incur major interference in qualitative analysis. The analysis was carried out under argon flow of 27.8 cc/min for the whole time with heating rate of 20°C/min up to 1000°C and 10°C/min from 1000°C to 1400°C. The sample was cooled naturally inside the furnace with argon flow of 27.8 cc/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XRD analysis

XRD analysis for sintered BR pellets and those reduced at 600°C is shown in Figure 4. Major phases in the sintered pellets were Brownmillerite ($\text{Al}_{0.441}\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_{1.559}\text{O}_5$), Gehlenite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{O}_7\text{Si}$), Lawsonite ($\text{Al}_2\text{CaO}_{10}\text{Si}_2$), Wollastonite (CaO_3Si), Melilite ($\text{Ca}_{5.95}\text{Na}_{2.05}\text{O}_{15}\text{Si}_4$), Perovskite (CaTiO_3) and Hematite (Fe_2O_3). Meanwhile major phases in the reduced pellets were Srebrodolskite ($\text{Ca}_2[\text{Fe,Al}]_2\text{O}_5$), Gehlenite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{O}_7\text{Si}$), Perovskite (CaTiO_3), Magnetite (Fe_3O_4), Wüstite (FeO) and metallic iron. Brownmillerite and Srebrodolskite peaks were in similar positions due to their similar chemical composition and both belongs to the Brownmillerite subgroup, but with different crystallography. Based on XRD analysis all the Brownmillerite phase in sintered pellets were transformed into Srebrodolskite during H₂ reduction process. It was also observed that most of the calcium silicate-containing phases in the sintered pellets were absorbed into Gehlenite during H₂ reduction, leaving only Gehlenite as the only calcium silicate-containing phase in reduced pellets.

FIG 4 – XRD analysis of sintered BR pellets and pellets reduced at 600°C.

By analysing chemical composition of the phases between sintered pellets and reduced pellets it can be concluded that only iron oxides were reduced during H₂ smelting reduction at 600°C. Magnetite and Wüstite peaks were observed in all the reduced pellets suggesting slow kinetics of the reduction reaction. Meanwhile metallic iron peaks were observed only in pellets reduced with 95 per cent H₂ – 5 per cent H₂O gas composition, suggesting that the equilibrium for reduction of metallic iron at 600°C exists between 85 per cent to 95 per cent H₂ and 5 per cent to 15 per cent H₂O gas composition.

DTA analysis

DTA analysis for sintered and reduced BR pellets is shown on Figure 5. There are 12 temperature points of interests which are signified by occurrence of troughs in DTA curves.

FIG 5 – DTA analysis of sintered BR pellets and pellets reduced at 600°C.

Phase equilibrium module of Factsage™ 8.1 was used to analyse and simulate melting process of sintered and reduced pellets. The simulation for sintered pellets was done based on chemical composition of XRF analysis for sintered pellets as shown in Table 3 in a basis of 100 g total mass. Whereas for simulation of reduced pellets 10 mol per cent and 5 mol per cent of initial Hematite composition in sintered pellets were converted into Wüstite and Magnetite, respectively. Amount of Wüstite and Magnetite for simulation of reduced pellets was estimated based on XRD result of BR pellets reduced at 600°C with 95 per cent H₂ – 5 per cent H₂O gas composition. Components input for simulation of reduced pellets is shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5

Components input for simulation of reduced BR pellets using Factsage™ 8.1.

Component	Mass (gr)	Component	Mass (gr)	Component	Mass (gr)
CaO	29.01	MnO	0.04	P ₂ O ₅	0.12
MgO	0.37	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.18	SO ₃	1.03
SiO ₂	7.66	V ₂ O ₅	0.15	ZrO ₂	0.11
Al ₂ O ₃	23.12	TiO ₂	3.87	SrO	0.03
Fe ₂ O ₃	25.94	NiO	0.06	Co ₃ O ₄	0.02
Fe ₃ O ₄	1.48	Na ₂ O	3.61	Total	99.65
FeO	2.75	K ₂ O	0.10		

The simulation was done from 300°C to 1400°C to investigate the temperature points of interests in the DTA curves. Resulting Factsage™ 8.1 phase equilibrium simulation for sintered pellets is shown on Figure 6 and result of simulation for reduced pellets is shown on Figure 7.

FIG 6 – Phase equilibrium simulation of sintered BR pellets from 300°C to 1400°C.

FIG 7 – Phase equilibrium simulation of reduced BR pellets from 300°C to 1400°C.

The first temperature point of interest occurred at $T \approx 350^\circ\text{C}$ was signified by occurrence of a small trough in DTA curve of sintered (unreduced) pellet. Based on Factsage™ 8.1 simulation, $\text{Ca}_5\text{P}_2\text{SiO}_{12}$ breaks down into tricalcium phosphate- β (CaP_2O_8) on the first temperature point of interest which is at $T \approx 350^\circ\text{C}$. It is proposed that excess calcia and silicon from the reaction immediately dissolved into either Bredigite ($\text{Ca}_7\text{Si}_4\text{MgO}_{16}$) or Rankinite ($\text{Ca}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$) in the system. The reaction that occurred on this temperature is shown in Equation (5):

Tricalcium phosphate- β is an unstable phase and based on the simulation its reverse reaction occurs at $T \approx 460^\circ\text{C}$, which is evidenced by occurrence of crest starting from $T \approx 470^\circ\text{C}$ on the DTA curve of sintered sample.

The second temperature point of interest occurred at $T \approx 425^\circ\text{C}$ where a trough occurred on DTA curve of the sample reduced with 85 per cent H_2 – 15 per cent H_2O gas composition. Formation of Bredigite from part of Olivine phase in the sample is supposed to occur around this temperature based on the simulation of sintered pellets. It is possible that olivine reacted with free CaO in the system to form Bredigite with excess magnesium oxide or iron oxide as shown in Equation (6):

The third temperature point of interest at $T \approx 475^\circ\text{C}$ is signified by occurrence of trough on DTA curve of sample reduced with 95 per cent H_2 – 5 per cent H_2O gas composition. Based on the simulation of reduced pellets a brief formation of Vanadium rich spinel occurred at $T \approx 480^\circ\text{C}$, however, it immediately breaks at $T \approx 500^\circ\text{C}$ which explains the occurrence of trough at this temperature.

The fourth temperature point of interest at $T \approx 540^\circ\text{C}$ is signified by occurrence of trough on DTA curve of the sintered sample and sample reduced with 75 per cent H_2 – 25 per cent H_2O gas composition. There was another nearby trough occurrence as well on the samples reduced with 85 per cent H_2 – 15 per cent H_2O and 95 per cent H_2 – 5 per cent H_2O gas composition, which suggests the same reaction is happening on all samples. Based on the simulation results of both sintered and reduced samples, transformation of potassium sulfate- α (K_2SO_4 - α) into potassium sulfate- β (K_2SO_4 - β) occurred around this temperature. The reaction is shown in Equation (7):

The fifth temperature point of interest is at $T \approx 620^\circ\text{C}$, which is signified by occurrence of trough on DTA curve of sample reduced with 95 per cent H_2 – 5 per cent H_2O gas composition. Considering its close proximity with the previous temperature point of interest and the sample is the only one with significant difference in chemical composition compared to other reduced samples, where it is the only one containing metallic Fe. There is a probability that the same reaction occurred where

potassium sulfate- α ($K_2SO_4\text{-}\alpha$) transformed into potassium sulfate- β ($K_2SO_4\text{-}\beta$) since there is no other change occurred in the simulation around 620°C.

The sixth temperature point of interest at $T \approx 810^\circ\text{C}$ is signified by the occurrence of trough on samples reduced with 75 per cent H_2 – 25 per cent H_2O and 85 per cent H_2 – 15 per cent H_2O gas composition. From the simulation of sintered samples it was observed that significant formation of calcium alumino ferrite ($Ca[Al,Fe]_6O_{10}$) and Rankinite occurred around this temperature. It is believed that part of Ca-rich spinel in the sample reacted with Andradite ($Ca_3Fe_2Si_3O_{12}$) and CaO in the system to form calcium alumino ferrite and Rankinite as shown in Equation (8):

The seventh temperature point of interest occurred at $T \approx 920^\circ\text{C}$, which signified by the occurrence of trough on DTA curve of sintered sample. Based on simulation of sintered sample, Celestite ($SrSO_4$) and $Na_2CaAl_4O_8$ starts to melt around this temperature to form slag phase which may explain the sudden increase in endothermic nature of the system. It is worth noting that Sr content in the sample is quite low hence only a few Sr-containing intermediate phases occurred in the simulation at a very low amount.

The eighth temperature point of interest is at $T \approx 1050^\circ\text{C}$, which is signified by occurrence of trough on DTA curve of sample reduced with 85 per cent H_2 – 15 per cent H_2O gas composition. Based on the simulation of reduced pellets, formation of sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) are supposed to occur around this temperature. It is proposed that $Na_2CaAl_4O_8$ in the system breaks down to form slag and reacts with free SO_3 in the system to form sodium sulfate as shown in Equation (9):

The ninth temperature point of interest at $T \approx 1150^\circ\text{C}$ is signified by the occurrence of trough on DTA curve of sample reduced with 85 per cent H_2 – 15 per cent H_2O and 95 per cent H_2 – 5 per cent H_2O gas composition which are followed by the occurrence of crest soon after, suggesting exothermic reaction occurred on the system. Based on the simulation of reduced sample a significant amount of calcium alumino ferrite and brownmillerite ($Ca_2[Al,Fe]_2O_5$) broke down to form slag around this temperature, which may explain the exothermic nature of the system.

The 10th and 11th temperature point of interest is occurring at $T \approx 1180^\circ\text{C}$ and $T \approx 1220^\circ\text{C}$, which is evidenced by occurrence of trough on DTA curve of all the samples. The close proximity between these temperatures suggests that a similar event is happening with small difference in chemical composition of the sample reduced with 95 per cent H_2 – 5 per cent H_2O due to presence of metallic iron in it causing the event to occur in a slightly lower temperature compared to others. Based on simulations of both sintered and reduced sample gas phase start to occur around these temperatures. The release of gas phase from solid components is generally exothermic which may explain formation of trough in the DTA system.

The 12th temperature point of interest is at $T \approx 1270^\circ\text{C}$, which signified by the occurrence of trough on DTA curve of sample reduced with 75 per cent H_2 – 25 per cent H_2O and 95 per cent H_2 – 5 per cent H_2O gas composition. Based on simulation of sintered samples transformation of Perovskite-A into Perovskite-B occurred around this temperature as shown in Equation (10):

Perovskite-A is a very stable phase which relatively remain unchanged from the beginning up to its transformation Perovskite-B. Meanwhile Perovskite-B is less stable than Perovskite-A and as soon as it formed it starts to slowly break down into slag phase.

Based on the simulation, most of the events occurred at each temperature point of interest should apply to all of the samples, however, due to the heterogenous nature of the sample and small amount of sample used in the analysis (~200 mg) obtaining uniform distribution of element in the sample is almost impossible, which explains why some events occurred in one sample but not on the other albeit similar phase composition based on XRD analysis.

TGA analysis

TGA analysis for sintered and reduced BR pellets is shown on Figure 8.

FIG 8 – TGA analysis of sintered BR pellets and pellets reduced at 600°C.

The curves in Figure 8 showed that there are three temperature points of interests where all of them are signified by significant increase in mass loss rate of the samples. All samples, both sintered and reduced, showed the same trend where the first significant increase in mass loss rate occurred at $T \approx 1080^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by the second significant increase in mass loss rate at $T \approx 1180^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the third significant increase in mass loss rate at $T \approx 1280^{\circ}\text{C}$. The same simulation results from Factsage™ 8.1 for sintered and reduced pellets was used to analyse the events happening on same temperature points of interest.

Based on simulation results, liquid slag formation starts to occur at $T \approx 900^{\circ}\text{C}$ for both sintered and reduced sample, however, the initial amount is really small since only Celestite and small amount of $\text{Ca}_5\text{P}_2\text{SiO}_{12}$ formed the slag at 900°C . At this point the slag consists of mostly CaO , CaS , SrO and SrS which originated from Celestite and $\text{Ca}_5\text{P}_2\text{SiO}_{12}$. It is not until $T \approx 1100^{\circ}\text{C}$ where the slag starts to pick up iron oxides in the system and increase its amount significantly with increasing temperature. It is proposed that most gases, which are trapped physically in the system are released during this process where larger number of solid phases are getting molten, forming the molten slag phase with lower viscosity and less hold-up potential, subsequently causing the first significant increase in mass loss rate of all systems at the first temperature point of interest which is at $T \approx 1080^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The second temperature point of interest is at $T \approx 1180^{\circ}\text{C}$ which correlates to the DTA curve where a trough which followed by crest occurred at similar temperature, as mentioned previously gas phase start to form around this temperature. To properly analyse composition of gas phase with increasing temperature from 1180°C to 1400°C another simulation was conducted using Factsage™ 8.1 with addition of 10 L of argon gas. Similar to simulation of phase equilibrium, components input for sintered pellets was done based on chemical composition of XRF analysis for sintered pellets as shown in Table 3 in a basis of 100 g total mass and simulation of reduced pellets was done using components input shown in Table 5. Resulting simulation for equilibrium of gas phase composition for sintered pellets is shown on Figure 9 and result of simulation for equilibrium of gas phase composition for reduced pellets is shown on Figure 10.

FIG 9 – Equilibrium simulation for gas phase composition of sintered BR pellets from 1180°C to 1400°C.

FIG 10 – Equilibrium simulation for gas phase composition of reduced BR pellets from 1180°C to 1400°C.

Based on simulation gas phase that are discharged by both sintered and reduced samples mainly consists of O₂ and SO₂ gas since partial pressure of other gases such as SO, SO₃, Na₂SO₄ and K₂SO₄ are at least lower by two orders compared to either O₂ or SO₂. Simulation for gas phase composition of sintered sample suggests that both O₂ and SO₂ gas are released at T = 1180°C meanwhile for simulation of gas phase composition of reduced sample the discharged gas consists of mostly SO₂ at T = 1180°C since partial pressure of O₂ at this temperature is lower by three orders. The difference in gas phase composition is due to reduced samples has significantly less chemically bonded O₂ since more O₂ has been removed during H₂ reduction leaving more chemically bonded SO₂ to be released into the atmosphere in comparison with O₂.

Based on the phase equilibrium simulation, the amount of gas phase in sintered samples is supposed to increase significantly with increasing temperature starting from T ≈ 1280°C and for reduced samples its amount of gas phase start to increase from T ≈ 1260°C. In correlation, simulation result for gas phase composition of sintered sample showed that partial pressure of O₂ starts to increase more significantly with increasing temperature at T = 1300°C, suggesting that higher

reaction kinetics starts to force higher amount of O₂ gas to be released from the sample despite of oxidative atmosphere due to existing SO₂ gas in the atmosphere, which eventually amplifies gas phase formation with increasing temperature. Simulation result for reduced sample also showed that partial pressure of O₂ is lower by less than one order compared to partial pressure of SO₂ at T ≥ 1320°C, increasing the likeliness for remaining O₂ in the sample to be discharged into the atmosphere. It is suggested that increased kinetics of gas phase formation and the release of remaining O₂ from the sample are followed by an increase in mass loss rate of the system which explains the third temperature point of interest at T ≈ 1280°C.

CONCLUSIONS

- Transformation of Brownmillerite into Srebrodolskite and dissolution of calcium silicate-containing phases into Gehlenite occurred during H₂ reduction of BR pellets.
- Ca₅P₂SiO₁₂ breaks down into tricalcium phosphate-β (CaP₂O₈), CaO and Silicone at T ≈ 350°C, however, since tricalcium phosphate-β is an unstable phase, it reverts into Ca₅P₂SiO₁₂ at T ≈ 460°C which are evidenced by corresponding trough and crest on DTA curve of sintered sample.
- Formation of Bredigite occurred at T ≈ 425°C where olivine reacted with CaO to form Bredigite. Significant amount of calcium alumino ferrite and Rankinite were formed at T ≈ 810°C which originates from Ca-rich spinel phase in the system. Na₂CaAl₄O₈ in the pellet yields molten slag and reacts with free SO₃ in the system to form sodium sulfate at T ≈ 1050°C.
- Transformation of potassium sulfate-α (K₂SO₄-α) into potassium sulfate-β (K₂SO₄-β) occurred at T ≈ 540°C and transformation of Perovskite-A into Perovskite-B occurred at T ≈ 1270°C.
- Initial formation of slag phase for both sintered and reduced pellets occurred at T = 900°C with a small liquid slag formation that contains mostly CaO, CaS, SrO and SrS. Amount of slag phase start to increase significantly with increasing temperature at T ≈ 1100°C where it starts to pick up iron oxides in the system which then followed by other oxides dissolution/melting in the system.
- Initial discharge of gas phase from both sintered and reduced pellets occurred at T ≈ 1180°C where sintered samples started to release both O₂ and SO₂ gas in the system and reduced samples released SO₂ gas. Amount of gas phase for both samples start to increase significantly with increasing temperature starting from T ≈ 1280°C when increased reaction kinetic forces remaining O₂ in the sample to be released into the atmosphere.

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